

Correlational Relationship of Nursing Professional Subjects and Board Exam Performance of Isabela State University-Echague November 2022 Nursing Licensure Examination Takers

Authors

¹Charlene R. Guillermo,
Student, Isabela State University-Main Campus,
Philippines

²Krista Marie T. Gumpal,
Student, Isabela State University-Main Campus,
Philippines

³Kristene Joy C. Guzman,
Student, Isabela State University-Main Campus,
Philippines

⁴Shyna Mae D. Iquin,
Student, Isabela State University-Main Campus,
Philippines

⁵Jessamae Leño,
Student, Isabela State University-Main Campus,
Philippines

⁶Efren O. Redon,
Student, Isabela State University-Main Campus,
Philippines

Co-Authors

⁷Markhipolito P. Galingana,
Faculty, Isabela State University-Main Campus,
Philippines

⁸Virgilio D. Ganadin
Jr., Faculty, Isabela State University-Main Campus,
Philippines

Adviser

⁹Markhipolito P. Galingana MAN, RN, RM
Isabela State University (ISU) Echague, Isabela

Abstract:- A study was conducted to examine the relationship between board performance and professional subjects among nursing graduates who took the Nursing Licensure Examination (NLE) in November 2022 from Isabela State University (ISU) Echague. The objective was to determine if there is a significant relationship between grades in undergraduate nursing professional subjects and board exam ratings. Data was collected from 100 respondents who recently completed their Bachelor of Science in nursing degree at ISU Echague using a quantitative research approach. The study analyzed their scores in professional subjects such as Medical-Surgical Nursing, Maternal and Child Health Nursing, Psychiatric Nursing, and Community Health Nursing to evaluate their performance on the PNLE. The overall weighted average and Nursing Practice 1–5 means were compared using a one-way ANOVA to see if any of those means differed statistically from the other. The findings showed that the respondents performed best in Intensive Nursing Practicum, a subject related to Nursing Practice III, IV, and V, but no significant relationship was found. The lowest performance was observed in Nursing Research 1, which covered Medical Surgical Nursing and Psychiatric Nursing in Nursing Practice III and had the lowest board exam rate. The study identified significant relationships between Health Assessment, Disaster Nursing, Care of Older Adult and

Psychiatric Nursing, indicating that higher academic performance in these subjects correlated with better board exam performance. This study examines factors affecting nursing graduates' board success and aims to improve curriculum and licensure readiness by linking professional subjects to board performance. It will benefit educators and curriculum developers in ensuring future nursing practitioners' competency.

Keywords:- Board Performance, Nursing Student, Undergraduate Professional Subjects, Nurse Licensure Exam, Relationship.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nursing students' journey doesn't end after graduation. In fact, it's just the beginning of their new milestone in the world of application, where the knowledge they have gained in their chosen course will come into use. Nursing graduates start on a lifelong learning path marked by continual professional growth and the acquisition of clinical skills as they move from the theoretical foundations of nursing to the practical world of healthcare. Every year, nursing graduates take up their NLE or the Nurse Licensure Examination, which they need in order to fully practice their nursing profession. Managed by the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC), the Philippine Nurse Licensure

Examination (PNLE) is composed of five (5) different subjects which give a total of 500 items that are in multiple-choice, effectively evaluating the board exam takers' comprehensive understanding and application of nursing competencies in accordance with Republic Act No. 9173 or the Philippine Nursing Act of 2022. The NLE serves as a crucial turning point in the careers of nursing graduates by demonstrating their readiness to provide patients with safe and competent care. The five subjects that are on the exam are; Basic Foundations of Nursing and Professional Nursing Practice, Community Health Nursing and Care of Healthy/At Risk Mother and Child, Care of Clients with Physiologic and Psychosocial Alterations (Part A), Care of Clients with Physiologic and Psychosocial Alterations (Part B), and Psychosocial Alterations (Part C). In each set, the examiner must score not less than sixty percent (60%) and a general average score of not lower than seventy-five percent (75%) in order to pass the exam.

The following are the performance of the Isabela State University Echague for the past five years, excluding the year 2020 due to the increased cases of the Covid-19 virus, prompting the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC) to postpone the scheduled licensure examinations. In 2018, the University was able to garner an institutional passing rate of 41.18% while having a national passing rate of 39.98%. In 2019, the institutional passing rate is 70.00% and the national passing rate is 55.20%. In 2021, the institutional passing rate is 45.45%, while the national passing rate is 51.45. And lastly, for the year 2022, the institutional passing rate is 90.00% and the national passing rate is 74.40%.

In the nursing course offered at Isabela State University-Echague, there are sixteen (16) undergraduate nursing professional subjects. These are; Fundamentals of Nursing Practice, Health Assessment; Community Health Nursing I; Community Health Nursing II; Care of Mother, Child, Adolescent (Well Clients); Care of Mother, Child, Adolescent (Acute and Chronic); Nursing Research I; Nursing Research II; Medical-Surgical Nursing I; Medical-Surgical Nursing II; Psychiatric Nursing; Care of Clients with Life Threatening Conditions, Acutely Ill/Multi-Organ Problems, High Acuity and Emergency Situation, Acute and Ill; Nursing Leadership and Management; Care of the Older Adult; Intensive Nursing Practicum; and Disaster Nursing. These subjects need to be taken in the duration of the whole program. According to section 1 of the CHED memorandum order no. 15 series of 2017 which is about the Policies, Standards and Guidelines for The Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) Program, the PSG "Allows HEIs offering BS Nursing program to customize the curriculum in accordance with the assessment of how best to achieve learning outcomes in their specific contexts and their respective missions." Most of the contents of the major subjects are what makes the board exam questions. There is a prevalent perception that excellent grades in academics are enough assurance that a person can perform well in his/her board examination. Academic grades can be a valuable indicator of how well they will perform on the board exams, as they demonstrate a student's knowledge and mastery of the subjects. Strong academic success often indicates an

effective knowledge foundation, which can be helpful for answering board exam questions. Therefore, it is safe to assume that academic performance can serve as a determinant for a graduate's board exam performance.

November 12 and 13 of the year 2022 is the schedule for the second batch of the Nursing Board Exam takers for the year 2022. First takers and retakers from all over the Philippines including the graduates of Isabela State University Echague Main Campus (ISU-E), took the said exam. The fresh graduates' performance was observed the moment the results of the 2022 NLE November takers were released in December. This allowed the researchers to determine the areas of improvement and enhancement as a requirement of the Accrediting Agency of Chartered Colleges and Universities in the Philippines (AACUP) which accredits curricular programs in the Philippines, especially colleges and state universities. Moreover, in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) Goal: 4, Quality Education, curriculum enhancement is of great help with ensuring competent skills, knowledge development, and effective education for the students. Also, the research is also in par with the University's Mission: "The Isabela State University is committed to develop globally competitive human, technological resources and services through quality instruction, innovative research, responsive community engagement and viable resource management programs for inclusive growth and sustainable development.", and also with its Vision: "A leading Research University in the ASEAN Region."

The results of this study will shed light on the variables influencing nursing graduates' success on the board. The study sought to contribute to the development of effective methods and interventions that can improve the nursing curriculum and the readiness of students for licensure examinations by establishing the link between professional subjects and board performance. For nursing educators and curriculum developers, the findings of this study will be helpful in guaranteeing the caliber and competency of future nursing practitioners.

The researchers sought to determine the general academic grades of the respondents' undergraduate nursing professional subjects. Also, to determine the licensure board exam of the respondents. Lastly, the researchers also sought to find out if there is a significant relationship between the general academic grades in undergraduate nursing professional subjects and board exam performance and rating.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational design. Data are collected with consent from the respondents and used to determine if there is a link between two or more variables. Moreover, the gathered data from the Google Form is described, discussed, and elaborated upon using the descriptive correlational design. The research study was conducted at the Isabela State University Echague Campus, San Fabian, Echague, Isabela, which is certified as ISO

9001:2015 by TUV SUD, specifically in the College of Nursing Department. Furthermore, the respondents of the study consist of Batch 2022 nursing graduates that took the Nursing Licensure Examination last November 2022 from Isabela State University- Echague Campus. A population of one hundred thirty-six (136) first-time takers was selected as the final respondents to the study. Out of one hundred thirty-six (136), there are one hundred five (125) who passed and eleven (11) takers who failed the board exam. Utilizing Slovin’s formula, the researchers gained a total of one hundred one (101) respondents. Finally, a simple random sampling technique was utilized to avoid biased selection. But only 100 respondents participated since one of the respondents is a transferee from a third-year college. The researchers used online platforms for survey questionnaires, specifically Google Surveys and Messenger, which were convenient to the respondents. Academic performance was also obtained from the college registrar upon the approval of the Dean and with the consent of the respondents. In connection with this, the researchers conducted a uniform procedure to ensure that the data will be geared towards the research objectives, and consent from the respondents is obtained. In addition, this study utilized the ISU-Echague Grading System: 1.0 is the highest grade, which is equivalent to 98–100%, followed by 1.25, which is equivalent to 95–97%, then 1.50, which is equivalent to 92–94%, followed by 1.75, which is equal to 89-91 %, 2.00 which is equal to 86-88 %, 2.25 which is equivalent to 83-85%, 2.50 which its equivalent is 80-82%, 2.75 which its equivalent is 77-79%, 3.00 which is equal to 75-76 % and the lowest grade is 5.0

which is below 75%. Furthermore, For the Statistical treatment, this study utilized frequency, percentage, mean, and chi-square to carefully analyze the gathered data. Finally, to ascertain if any of the means of the General Weighted Average and Nursing Practice 1–5 differ statistically from one another, a one-way ANOVA was employed to compare the means. It examines the null hypothesis specifically. Accept the alternative hypothesis (Ha), which states that there are at least two group means that are statistically distinct from one another, if the one-way ANOVA yields a statistically significant result.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data that have been evaluated with SPSS version 16.0 are presented in this chapter. Moreover, it reveals the findings of the study which answer the problems presented earlier in Chapter 1 that researchers sought to find for answers. Through the use of various statistical tests, analyzed data were gathered followed by either accepting or rejecting the claims or hypotheses. The analyses of the data are then further explained in this chapter through discussions of the results found together with specific related literatures or studies which either supports or contradicts the claim and other supporting given information and proofs in the tool employed.

A. General Academic Grades of the Respondents in Terms of Undergraduate Professional Subject

➤ *Fundamentals of Nursing Practice*

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage of Fundamentals of Nursing Practice

GWA	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
92-94	1	1.00
86-88	9	9.00
83-85	15	15.00
80-82	35	35.00
77-79	25	25.00
75-76	15	15.00
Total	100	100.0
Mean score: 80.53		

Fig 1 Frequency and Percentage of Fundamentals of Nursing Practice

The table and figure above indicate that 1 nursing graduate which makes up 1 percent has a General Weighted Average ranging in 92-94%. On the other hand, there are 9 respondents which constitutes to 9 percent that has an average ranging in 86-88%. On rating ranging from 83-85% and 80-82% it accumulated a respondents and percentage of 15 and 35. Also, there are 25 percent or 25 respondents who got an average ranging from 77-79%. Moreover, there are 15 respondents or 15 percent has a General Weighted Average ranging in 75-76%

As can be obtained from the table, there is a much greater number of Nursing Graduates in the Isabela State University Echague Campus who garnered a General Weighted Average ranging from 80-82% in Fundamentals of Nursing Practice.

➤ *Health Assessment*

Table 2 Frequency and Percentage of Health Assessment

GWA	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
95-97	3	3.00
92-94	11	11.00
89-91	20	20.00
86-88	38	38.00
83-85	21	21.00
80-82	7	7.00
Total	100	100.0
Mean score: 87.48		

Fig 2 Frequency and Percentage of Health Assessment

The table and figure above indicate that 3 respondents with a percentage of 3 had a rating within the range of 95-97%. On rating ranging from 92-94% and 89-91% it accumulated 11 percentage and respondents. Additionally, there are 38 students with a percent of 38 got an 86-88% General Weighted Average, along with 21 students who got a 21 percent got an average ranging from 83-85. Moreover, 7 respondents which make up 7 percent had a rating within the range of 80-82% General Weighted Average.

As can be gleaned, majority of Nursing Graduates in the Isabela State University Echague Campus have a General Weighted Average ranging from 86-88% in Health Assessment.

➤ *Community Health Nursing I*

Table 3 Frequency and Percentage of Community Health Nursing I

GWA	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
92-94	5	5.00
89-91	15	15.00
86-88	39	39.00
83-85	33	33.00
80-82	8	8.00
Total	100	100.0
Mean score: 86.28		

Fig 3 Frequency and Percentage of Community Health Nursing I

The table and figure above indicate that 5 respondents with a percentage of 5 had a rating within the range of 92-94%. On rating ranging from 89-91% and 86-88% it accumulated 15 and 39 percentage from 15 and 39 respondents. Furthermore, there are 33 students with a percent of 33 got an 83-85% General Weighted Average as well as 8 respondents which make up 8 percent had a rating within the range of 80-82% General Weighted Average.

As can be seen, majority of Nursing Graduates in the Isabela State University Echague Campus have a General Weighted Average ranging from 86-88% in Community Health Nursing I.

➤ *Community Health Nursing II*

Table 4 Frequency and Percentage of Community Health Nursing II

GWA	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
92-94	7	7.00
89-91	13	13.00
86-88	42	42.00
83-85	37	37.00
80-82	1	1.00
Total	100	100.0
Mean score:86.64		

Fig 4 Frequency and Percentage of Community Health Nursing II

The table and figure above specify that 7 respondents with a percentage of 7 had a rating within the range of 92-94%. On rating ranging from 89-91% and 86-88% it accumulated 13 and 42 percentage from 13 and 42 respondents. Furthermore, there are 37 students with a percent of 37 got an 83-85% General Weighted Average as well as 1 respondent which make up 1 percent had a rating within the range of 80-82% General Weighted Average.

As can be observed, majority of Nursing Graduates in the Isabela State University Echague Campus have a General Weighted Average ranging from 86-88% in Community Health Nursing II.

➤ *Care of Mother, Child, Adolescent (Well Clients)*

Table 5 Frequency and Percentage of Care of Mother, Child, Adolescent (Well Clients)

GWA	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
95-97	1	1.00
89-91	9	9.00
86-88	20	20.00
83-85	32	32.00
80-82	29	29.00
77-79	8	8.00
75-76	1	1.00
Total	100	100.0
Mean score: 83.82		

Fig 5 Frequency and Percentage of Care of Mother, Child, Adolescent (Well Clients)

The table above specify that 1 respondent with a percentage of 1 had a rating within the range of 95-97%. On rating ranging from 89-91% and 86-88% it accumulated 9 and 20 percentage from 9 and 20 respondents. Along with 32 students with a percentage of 32 got a grade ranging from 83-85%, aside from that, there are also 29 students with a percentage of 29 got a grade of 80-82%. On the next rating, there are 37 students with a percent of 37 got an 83-85% General Weighted Average as well as 1 respondent which make up 1 percent had a rating within the range of 80-82%. Furthermore, 8 percent from 8 respondents got rating ranging from 77-79% as well as for the rating of 75-76%, only 1 student has this general weighted average.

As can be seen, majority of Nursing Graduates in the Isabela State University Echague Campus have a General Weighted Average ranging from 83-85% in Care of Mother, Child, Adolescent (Well Clients).

➤ *Care of Mother, Child, Adolescent (Acute and Chronic)*

Table 6 Frequency and Percentage of Care of Mother, Child, Adolescent (Acute and Chronic)

GWA	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
89-91	7	7.00
86-88	34	34.00
83-85	35	35.00
80-82	19	19.00
77-79	5	5.00
Total	100	100.0
Mean score: 84.57		

Fig 6 Frequency and Percentage of Care of Mother, Child, Adolescent (Acute and Chronic)

The table and figure above indicate that 7 nursing graduates which makes up to 7 percent has a General Weighted Average ranging in 89-91%. On the other hand, there are 34 respondents which constitutes to 34 percent that has an average ranging in 86-88%. On rating ranging from 83-85% and 80-82% it accumulated a respondents and percentage of 35 and 19. Also, there are 5 percent or 5 respondents who got a General weighted average ranging from 77-79%.

As can be obtained, majority of Nursing Graduates in the Isabela State University Echague Campus have a General Weighted Average ranging from 83-85% in Care of Mother, Child, Adolescent (Acute and Chronic).

➤ *Nursing Research I*

Table 7 Frequency and Percentage of Nursing Research I

GWA	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
92-94	1	1.00
89-91	2	2.00
86-88	8	8.00
83-85	7	7.00
80-82	30	30.00
77-79	28	28.00
75-76	24	24.00
Total	100	100.0
Mean score: 79. 83		

Fig 7 Frequency and Percentage of Nursing Research I

The table and figure above indicate that 1 nursing graduate which makes up to 1 percent has a General Weighted Average ranging in 92-94%. On the other hand, there are 2 respondents which constitutes to 2 percent that has an average ranging in 89-91%. On rating ranging from 86-88% and 83-85% it accumulated a respondents and percentage of 8 and 7. Also, there are 30 percent or 30 respondents who got an 80-82%. Additionally, there are 28 and 24 respondents which indicates 28 and 24 percent of them got a General Weighted Average of 77-79% as well as 75-76%

As can be seen, majority of Nursing Graduates in the Isabela State University Echague Campus have a General Weighted Average ranging from 80-82% in Nursing Research I.

➤ *Nursing Research II*

Table 8 Frequency and Percentage of Nursing Research II

GWA	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
98-100	1	1.00
95-97	14	14.00
92-94	36	36.00
89-91	5	5.00
86-88	1	1.00
77-79	1	1.00
75-76	42	42.00
Total	100	100.0
Mean score: 85.77		

Fig 8 Frequency and Percentage of Nursing Research II

The table and figure above indicate that 1 nursing graduate which makes up to 1 percent has a General Weighted Average ranging in 98-100%. On the other hand, there are 24 respondents which constitutes to 14 percent has an average ranging in 95-97%. On rating ranging from 92-94% and 89-91% it accumulated a respondents and percentage of 36 and 5. Also, there are 1 percent or 1 respondent who got an 86-88%.as well as 1 percent or 1 respondent whose average was 77-79% Additionally, there are 42 respondents which indicates 42 percent of them got a General Weighted Average of 75-76%

As can be obtained, majority of Nursing Graduates in the Isabela State University Echague Campus have a General Weighted Average ranging from 75-76% in Nursing Research II.

➤ *Medical-Surgical Nursing I*

Table 9 Frequency and Percentage of Medical-Surgical Nursing I

GWA	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
86-88	8	8.00
83-85	35	35.00
80-82	27	27.00
77-79	30	30.00
Total	100	100.0
Mean score: 81.63		

Fig 9 Frequency and Percentage of Medical-Surgical Nursing I

The table and figure above specify that 8 respondents with a percentage of 8 had a rating within the range of 86-88%. On rating ranging from 83-85% it accumulated 35 percentage from 35 respondents. Along with 27 students with a percentage of 27 got a grade ranging from 80-82%. Furthermore, 30 percent from 30 respondents got a general weighted average from 77-79%.

As can be seen, majority of Nursing Graduates in the Isabela State University Echague Campus have a General Weighted Average ranging from 83-85% in Medical-Surgical Nursing I.

➤ *Medical-Surgical Nursing II*

Table 10 Frequency and Percentage of Medical-Surgical Nursing II

GWA	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
92-94	3	3.00
89-91	10	10.00
86-88	14	14.00
83-85	29	29.00
80-82	16	16.00
77-79	22	22.00
75-76	6	6.00
Total	100	100.0
Mean score: 82.98		

Fig 10 Frequency and Percentage of Medical-Surgical Nursing II

The table and figure above specify that 3 respondents with a percentage of 3 had a rating within the range of 92-94%. On rating ranging from 89-91% and 86-88% it accumulated 10 and 14 percentage from 10 and 14 respondents. On the other hand, there are 29 percentage from 29 respondents who got 83-85%. In addition, 16 percent from 16 respondents got a rating got an 80-82% rating as well as there are 22 and 6 respondents with a percentage of 22 and 6 got a General Weighted Average within 77-79% and 75-76%.

As can be gleaned, majority of Nursing Graduates in the Isabela State University Echague Campus have a General Weighted Average ranging from 83-85% in Medical-Surgical Nursing II.

➤ *Psychiatric Nursing*

Table 11 Frequency and Percentage of Psychiatric Nursing

GWA	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
92-94	7	7.00
89-91	16	16.00
86-88	53	53.00
83-85	20	20.00
80-82	4	4.00
Total	100	100.0
Mean score: 87.18		

Fig 11 Frequency and Percentage of Psychiatric Nursing

The table and figure above specify that 7 respondents with a percentage of 7 had a rating within the range of 92-94%. On rating ranging from 89-91% it accumulated 16 percentage from 16 respondents. Along with 53 students with a percentage of 53 got a grade ranging from 86-88%. On the other hand, there are 20 students with 20 percentage got grade ranging from 83-85%. Furthermore, 4 percent from 4 respondents got a general weighted average from 80-82%.

As can be observed, majority of Nursing Graduates in the Isabela State University Echague Campus have a General Weighted Average ranging from 86-88% in Psychiatric Nursing.

➤ *Care of Clients with life Threatening Conditions, Acutely Ill/Multi-Organ Problems, High Acuity and Emergency Situation, Acute and Ill*

Table 12 Frequency and Percentage of Care of Clients with Life Threatening Conditions, Acutely Ill/Multi-Organ Problems, High Acuity, and Emergency situation, Acute and Ill

GWA	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
92-94	1	1.00
89-91	18	18.00
86-88	31	31.00
83-85	34	34.00
80-82	13	13.00
77-79	3	3.00
Total	100	100.0
Mean score: 85.53		

Fig 12 Frequency and Percentage of Care of Clients with Life Threatening Conditions, Acutely Ill/Multi-Organ Problems, High Acuity, and Emergency situation, Acute and Ill

The table and figure above indicate that 1 nursing graduate which makes up to 1 percent has a General Weighted Average ranging in 92-94%. On the other hand, there are 18 respondents which constitutes to 18 percent has an average ranging in 89-91%. On rating ranging from 86-88% and 83-85% it accumulated a respondents and percentage of 31 and 34. Also, there are 13 percent or 13 respondents who got an 80-82%.as well as 3 percent or 3 respondent whose average was 77-79%. Moreover, there are only 3 students with 3 percentage got a General Weighted Average of 77-79%

As can be gleaned, majority of Nursing Graduates in the Isabela State University Echague Campus have a General Weighted Average ranging from 83-85% in Care of Clients with Life Threatening Conditions, Acutely Ill/Multi-Organ Problems, High Acuity, and Emergency situation, Acute and Ill.

➤ *Nursing Leadership and Management*

Table 13 Frequency and Percentage of Nursing Leadership and Management

GWA	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
95-97	4	4.00
92-94	21	21.00
89-91	41	41.00
86-88	15	15.00
83-85	13	13.00
80-82	6	6.00
Total	100	100.0
Mean score: 89.1		

Fig 13 Frequency and Percentage of Nursing Leadership and Management

The table and figure above specify that 4 respondents with a percentage of 4 had a rating within the range of 95-97%. On rating ranging from 92-94% and 89-91% it accumulated 21 and 41 percentage from 21 and 41 respondents. Along with 15 students with a percentage of 15 got a grade ranging from 86-88%, On the next rating, there are 13 students with a percent of 13 got an 83-85% General Weighted Average. Furthermore, 6 percent from 6 respondents got a rating ranging from 80-82%.

As can be seen, majority of Nursing Graduates in the Isabela State University Echague Campus have a General Weighted Average ranging from 89-91% in Nursing Leadership and Management.

➤ *Care of the Older Adult*

Table 14 Frequency and Percentage of Care of the Older Adult

GWA	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
95-97	2	2.00
92-94	15	15.00
89-91	43	43.00
86-88	34	34.00
83-85	6	6.00
Total	100	100.0
Mean score: 89.19		

Fig 14 Frequency and Percentage of Care of the Older Adult

The table and figure above indicate that only 2 respondents with a percentage of 2 had a rating within the range of 95-97 %. On rating ranging from 92-94% and 89-91% it accumulated 15 and 43 percentage from 15 and 43 respondents. Additionally, there are 34 students with a percentage of 34 got an 86-88% rating. Moreover, there are 6 students with a percent of 6 got an 83-85% General Weighted Average.

As can be gleaned, majority of Nursing Graduates in the Isabela State University Echague Campus have a General Weighted Average ranging from 89-91% in Care of the Older Adult.

➤ *Intensive Nursing Practicum*

Table 15 Frequency and Percentage of Intensive Nursing Practicum

GWA	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
95-97	6	6.00
92-94	37	37.00
89-91	38	38.00
86-88	18	18.00
83-85	1	1.00
Total	100	100.0
Mean score: 90.87		

Fig 15 Frequency and Percentage of Intensive Nursing Practicum

The table and figure above indicate that 6 respondents with a percentage of 6 had a rating within the range of 95-97 %. On rating ranging from 92-94% and 89-91% it accumulated 37 and 38 percentage from 37 and 38 respondents. Additionally, there are 18 students with a percentage of 18 got an 86-88% rating. Moreover, there are 1 student with a percent of 1 got an 83-85% General Weighted Average.

As can be observed, majority of Nursing Graduates in the Isabela State University Echague Campus have a General Weighted Average ranging from 89-91% in Intensive Nursing Practicum.

➤ *Disaster Nursing*

Table 16 Frequency and Percentage of Disaster Nursing

GWA	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
95-97	2	2.00
92-94	3	3.00
89-91	6	6.00
86-88	15	15.00
83-85	18	18.00
80-82	14	14.00
77-79	38	38.00
75-76	4	4.00
Total	100	100.0
Mean score: 82.28		

Fig 16 Frequency and Percentage of Disaster Nursing

B. Determine the licensure board exam rating of the respondents to;

➤ *Nursing Practice I – Fundamentals of Nursing Practice/Health Assessment*

Table 17 Nursing Practice I – Fundamentals of Nursing Practice/Health Assessment

RATING	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
85-92	49	49.0
77-84	47	47.0
69-76	4	4.0
Total	100	100.0
MEAN SCORE = 84.10		

Fig 17 Nursing Practice I – Fundamentals of Nursing Practice/ Health Assessment

The table shows that in Nursing Practice 1, forty-nine respondents, in which 49% of the sample got 85-92 % rating. Furthermore, forty-seven of the respondents in which 47% of the sample got a grade of 77-84 % rating. Moreover, it shows that 4 of the respondents in which 4% got 69-76% rating. The mean score in this test category is 84.10 %.

➤ *Nursing Practice II – Care of Health/ At Risk Mother and Child/ Community Health Nursing*

Table 18 Nursing Practice II – Care of Health/ At Risk Mother and Child/ Community Health Nursing

RATING	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
85-92	21	21.0
77-84	73	73.0
69-76	6	6.0
Total	100	100.0
MEAN SCORE = 81.70		

Fig 18 Nursing Practice II – Care of Health/ At Risk Mother and Child/Community Health Nursing

In Nursing Practice II, twenty-one respondents in which 21% of the sample got 85-92 % rating. Furthermore, seventy-three of the respondents in which 73% of the sample got a grade of 77-84 % rating. Moreover, it shows that 6 of the respondents in which 6% got 69-76% rating. The mean score in this test category is 81.70 %.

➤ *Nursing Practice III – Care of Clients with Physiologic and Psychosocial Alterations (Part A)*

Table 19 Nursing Practice III (Care of Clients with Physiological and Psychosocial Alteration)

RATING	FREQUENCY	PERCENT	RATING
85-92	6	6.0	85-92
77-84	66	66.0	77-84
69-76	19	19.0	69-76
61-68	8	8.0	61-68
50-60	1	1.0	50-60
Total	100	100.0	Total
MEAN SCORE = 77.93			MEAN SCORE = 77.93

Fig 19 Nursing Practice III (Care of Clients with Physiological and Psychosocial Alteration) (Part A)

In Nursing Practice III, six respondents in which 6% of the sample got 85-92 % rating. In addition, 66 respondents, or 66% of the sample, received a rating of 77-84%. Further, it demonstrates that of the 19 respondents, 19% received ratings between 69 and 76%. Also, 8 of the respondents, or 8% of the respondents, had a rating of 61-68%. Finally, just one respondent—representing 1% of the sample—received a rating of 50% to 60%. In this test category, the mean score is 77.93%.

➤ *Nursing Practice IV – Care of Clients with Physiologic and Psychosocial Alterations (Part B)*

Table 20 Nursing Practice IV (Care of Clients with Physiologic and Psychosocial Alterations (Part B)

RATING	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
85-92	5	5.0
77-84	74	74.0
69-76	18	18.0
61-68	3	3.0
Total	100	100.0
MEAN SCORE = 78.98		

Fig 20 Nursing Practice IV (Care of Clients with Physiologic and Psychosocial Alterations (Part B)

In Nursing Practice IV, five respondents in which 5% of the sample received scores between 85 and 92%. In addition, seventy-four respondents or 74% of the sample, received ratings of 77-84%. Additionally, it demonstrates that 18 of the respondents or 18% received a rating of 69-76%. Finally, three respondents, or 3% of the sample, received ratings of 61-68%. In this exam category, the mean score is 78.98.

➤ Nursing Practice V – Care of Clients with Physiologic and Psychosocial Alterations (Part C)

Table 21 Nursing Practice V (Care of Clients with Physiologic and Psychosocial Alterations (Part C))

RATING	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
85-92	4	4.0
77-84	73	73.0
69-76	18	18.0
61-68	4	4.0
50-60	1	1.0
Total	100	100.0
MEAN SCORE = 78.49		

Fig 21 Nursing Practice V (Care of Clients with Physiologic and Psychosocial Alterations (Part C))

In Nursing Practice V, four respondents in which 4% of the sample got 85-92 % rating. Furthermore, seventy-three of the respondents in which 73% of the sample got a grade of 77-84 % rating. Moreover, it shows that eighteen of the respondents in which 18% got 69-76% rating. In addition, four respondents in which 4% of the sample got 61-68% rating. Lastly only 1 respondent in which 1 % of the sample got 50-60% rating The mean score in this test category is 78.49 %.

Table 22 Isabela State University-Echague November 2022 NLE Rating

RATING	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
91-95	1	1.0
85-90	5	5.0
80-84	51	51.0
75-79	37	37.0
70 below	6	6.0
Total	100	100.0
MEAN SCORE = 79.82		

Fig 22 Isabela State University Echague November 2022 NLE Rating

In ISU Echague November 2022 NLE Rating, 1 respondent in which 1 % of the sample got 91-95 % rating. Furthermore, 5 of the respondents, in which 5% of the sample got a grade of 85-90 % rating. Moreover, it shows that fifty-one of the respondents in which 51 % got 80-84% rating. In addition, thirty-seven respondents, 37% of the sample got 75-79% rating. Lastly only 6 respondents in which 6 % of the sample got below 70% rating. The mean score in in ISU Echague November 2022 NLE Rating is 79.82%.

C. Significant Relationship Between the General Academic Grades in Undergraduate Nursing Professional Subjects and Board Exam Rating.

- Significant Relationship Between General Weighted Average of Fundamentals of Nursing Practice, Health Assessment, Nursing Research I, and Nursing Research II to Nursing Practice I.

Table 23 Correlation of General Weighted Average of Fundamentals of Nursing Practice, Health Assessment, Nursing research I, and Nursing research II to Nursing Practice I

	Nursing Practice I	
	χ^2	
Fundamentals of Nursing Practice	13.68 ^{ns}	Fundamentals of Nursing Practice
Health Assessment	25.19**	Health Assessment
Nursing research I	11.01 ^{ns}	Nursing research I
Nursing research II	6.24 ^{ns}	Nursing research II

^{ns}- (Not significant)
 * (Significant)
 ** (Highly significant)

The table above shows the correlation of the General Weighted Average of undergraduate nursing professional subjects particularly, Fundamentals of Nursing Practice, Health Assessment, Nursing research I, and Nursing research II to Nursing Practice I, one of the components of the Nursing Licensure Examination. It revealed that out of the four subjects, only Health Assessment gained a highly significant relationship with Nursing Practice I since the p-value is 0.005 which is less than the level of significance 0.05. It only means that as their Health Assessment academic performance increases, their board examination performance in NP1 with respect to the subject also increases. It is corroborated by a research by Llego et al. (2020), which found that nursing graduates' academic performance—including their grades in NCM and RLE

courses and on the Pre-Board Examination—had a minor impact on their ability to pass the Philippine Nurse Licensure Examination. Grade in NCM courses has the highest predictive value in passing the Philippine NLE. However, this interpretation is contradicted by the study of Soriano (2016) stating that there's no significant relationship of NCM 100, HA, NCM 105, NCM 106, CHN and CA II with p values >0.05.

- Significant Relationship Between General Weighted Average of Care of Mother, Child and Adolescent (Well Client), Care of Mother, Child and Adolescent (Acute and Chronic), Community Health Nursing I, Community Health Nursing II, Nursing Research I, and Nursing Research II to Nursing Practice II.

Table 24 Correlation of General Weighted Average of Care of Mother, Child and Adolescent (Well Client), Care of Mother, Child and Adolescent (Acute and Chronic), Community Health Nursing I, Community Health Nursing II, Nursing research I, and Nursing research II to Nursing Practice II.

	Nursing Practice II	
	χ^2	
Care of Mother, Child and Adolescent (Well Client)	6.53 ^{ns}	Care of Mother, Child and Adolescent (Well Client)
Care of Mother, Child and Adolescent (Acute and Chronic)	5.79 ^{ns}	Care of Mother, Child and Adolescent (Acute and Chronic)
Community Health Nursing I	8.82 ^{ns}	Community Health Nursing I
Community Health Nursing II	12.23 ^{ns}	Community Health Nursing II
Nursing research I	9.53 ^{ns}	Nursing research I
Nursing research II	8.86 ^{ns}	Nursing research II

^{ns}- (Not significant)
 * (Significant)
 ** (Highly significant)

The table above shows the correlation of General Weighted Average of undergraduate nursing professional subjects particularly, Care of Mother, Child and Adolescent (Well Client), Child and Adolescent (Well Client), Care of Mother, Child and Adolescent (Acute and Chronic), Community Health Nursing I, Community Health Nursing II, Nursing research I and Nursing research II to Nursing Practice II, one of the components of Nursing Licensure Examination. It revealed that all of them has no significant

relationship with Nursing Practice II. It only means that the said undergraduate nursing professional subjects has no bearing on the board examination performance. It is supported by the study conducted by Lamasan et al. (2018) that in terms of Patient Care Competencies, Empowering Competencies, Enhancing Competencies, and Enabling Competencies, UPHSL nursing graduates performed proficiently in their key competency areas. The researchers concluded that there is no significant relationship between

Nursing Practice 1 (NP1) to Academic Performance in CHN, NCM100 as to Nursing Practice 4 (NP4) to NCM103, NCM104 and NCM106, and are independent and has no influence to each other, however there is no significant relationship in Nursing Practice 2 (NP2) to NCM101 and NCM102, Nursing Practice 3(NP3) to NCM103 and NCM104, Nursing Practice 5 (NP5) to NCM105, RESI and RES1. The researchers came to the conclusion that the academic performance of CHN, NCM100, NCM101, NCM102, NCM103, NCM104, NCM105, NCM106, RES1, RES2, and is independent of and has no bearing on the performance of core competency.

➤ *Significant Relationship Between General Weighted Average of Medical Surgical Nursing I, Medical Surgical Nursing II, Nursing Leadership and Management, Disaster Nursing, Psychiatric Nursing, Care of Older Adult, Care of Clients with Life Threatening Conditions, Acuity Ill/ Multi-Organ Progress High Acuity Emergency Situation, Acuity and Ill, Intensive Nursing Practicum, Nursing Research I, and Nursing Research II To Nursing Practice III.*

Table 25 Correlation of General Weighted Average of Medical Surgical Nursing I, Medical Surgical Nursing II, Nursing Leadership and Management, Disaster Nursing, Psychiatric Nursing, Care of Older Adult, Care of Clients with Life Threatening Conditions, Acuity Ill/ Multi-Organ Progress High Acuity Emergency Situation, Acuity and Ill, Intensive Nursing Practicum, Nursing Research I, and Nursing Research II to Nursing Practice III.

	Nursing Practice III	
	χ^2	
Medical Surgical Nursing I	12.83 ^{ns}	Medical Surgical Nursing I
Medical Surgical Nursing II	21.10 ^{ns}	Medical Surgical Nursing II
Nursing Leadership and Management	20.71 ^{ns}	Nursing Leadership and Management
Disaster Nursing	22.02 ^{ns}	Disaster Nursing
Psychiatric Nursing	11.50 ^{ns}	Psychiatric Nursing
Nursing research I	18.23 ^{ns}	Nursing research I
Nursing research II	15.71 ^{ns}	Nursing research II
Care of Older Adult	25.74 ^{ns}	Care of Older Adult
Care of Older Adult, Care of Clients with Life threatening conditions, Acuity ill/ multi-organ progress High Acuity Emergency situation, Acuity and ill	21.38 ^{ns}	Care of Older Adult, Care of Clients with Life threatening conditions, Acuity ill/ multi-organ progress High Acuity Emergency situation, Acuity and ill
Intensive Nursing Practicum	10.26 ^{ns}	Intensive Nursing Practicum

^{ns}- (Not significant)
 * (Significant)
 ** (Highly significant)

The table above shows the correlation of the General Weighted Average of undergraduate nursing professional subjects particularly, Medical Surgical Nursing I, Medical Surgical Nursing II, Nursing Leadership and Management, Disaster Nursing, Psychiatric Nursing, Nursing research I, Nursing research II, Care of Older Adult, Care of Older Adult, Care of Clients with Life threatening conditions, Acuity ill/ multi-organ progress High Acuity Emergency situation, Acuity and ill and Intensive Nursing Practicum to Nursing Practice III, one of the components of Nursing Licensure Examination. It revealed that all of them have no significant relationship with Nursing Practice II. It only means that the said undergraduate nursing professional subjects have nothing to do with the board examination performance. Nursing Practice III has the lowest rate in batches, despite being the hardest part of the NLE. It was supported by the study conducted by Lamasan et al. (2018) that in terms of Patient Care Competencies, Empowering Competencies, Enhancing Competencies, and Enabling Competencies, UPHSL nursing graduates performed proficiently in their key competency areas. The researchers concluded that Nursing Practice 1 (NP1) and Academic

Performance in CHN, NCM100 as well as Nursing Practice 4 (NP4) and NCM103, NCM104, and NCM106 are not significantly correlated with one another; on the other hand, Nursing Practice 2 (NP2) and NCM101 and NCM102, Nursing Practice 3 (NP3) and NCM103 and NCM104, and Nursing Practice 5 (NP5) and NCM105, RESI, and RES1 are not significantly correlated with one another. We came to the conclusion that the academic achievement of RES1, RES2, NCM100, NCM101, NCM102, NCM103, NCM104, NCM105, NCM106, and CHN is unrelated to and unaffected by the execution of core competencies.

➤ *Significant Relationship Between General Weighted Average of Medical Surgical Nursing I, Medical Surgical Nursing II, Nursing Leadership and Management, Disaster Nursing, Psychiatric Nursing, Care of Older Adult, Care of Clients with Life Threatening Conditions, Acuity Ill/ Multi-Organ Progress High Acuity Emergency Situation, Acuity and Ill, Intensive Nursing Practicum, Nursing Research I, and Nursing Research II To Nursing Practice IV*

Table 26 Correlation of General Weighted Average of Medical Surgical Nursing I, Medical Surgical Nursing II, Nursing Leadership and Management, Disaster Nursing, Psychiatric Nursing, Care of Older Adult, Care of Clients with Life Threatening Conditions, Acuity Ill/ Multi-Organ Progress High Acuity Emergency Situation, Acuity and Ill, Intensive Nursing Practicum, Nursing Research I, and Nursing Research II To Nursing Practice IV.

	Nursing Practice IV	
	χ^2	
Medical Surgical Nursing I	4.97 ^{ns}	Medical Surgical Nursing I
Medical Surgical Nursing II	18.31 ^{ns}	Medical Surgical Nursing II
Nursing Leadership and Management	15.56 ^{ns}	Nursing Leadership and Management
Disaster Nursing	26.27**	Disaster Nursing
Psychiatric Nursing	14.60 ^{ns}	Psychiatric Nursing
Nursing research I	9.57 ^{ns}	Nursing research I
Nursing research II	13.87 ^{ns}	Nursing research II
Care of Older Adult	12.005 ^{ns}	Care of Older Adult
Care of Older Adult, Care of Clients with Life threatening conditions, Acuity ill/ multi-organ progress High Acuity Emergency situation, Acuity and Ill	16.708 ^{ns}	Care of Older Adult, Care of Clients with Life threatening conditions, Acuity ill/ multi-organ progress High Acuity Emergency situation, Acuity and Ill
Intensive Nursing Practicum	15.15 ^{ns}	Intensive Nursing Practicum

^{ns}- (Not significant)
 * (Significant)
 ** (Highly significant)

The table above shows the correlation of General Weighted Average of undergraduate nursing professional subjects particularly, Medical Surgical Nursing I, Medical Surgical Nursing II, Nursing Leadership and Management, Disaster Nursing, Psychiatric Nursing, Nursing research I, Nursing research II, Care of Older Adult, Care of Older Adult, Care of Clients with Life threatening conditions, Acuity ill/ multi-organ progress High Acuity Emergency situation, Acuity and Ill and Intensive Nursing Practicum to Nursing Practice IV, one of the components of Nursing Licensure Examination. It revealed that out of the ten subjects, only Disaster Nursing has highly significant relationship with Nursing Practice IV which has level of significance 0.010. Therefore, as their Disaster Nursing academic performance increases, their board examination performance in NP IV with respect to the subject also increases. This conclusion is refuted by the study performed by Neri (2009) that underlined that although graduates succeed in hurdling the test, they acquire poor passing

scores and that the lowest scores are in the areas of Medical-Surgical Nursing topics. According to Rosales, Arugay, Divina Gracia, and Palaganas (2014) this is a reflection of the absence of learning experiences and competencies of nursing board examinees brought about by restricted learning hospitals. This outcome also agrees with the findings of De Leon (2016), Palaganas, Divina Gracia, and Rosales (2013), and De Leon et al. (2016).

➤ *Significant Relationship Between General Weighted Average of Medical Surgical Nursing I, Medical Surgical Nursing II, Nursing Leadership and Management, Disaster Nursing, Psychiatric Nursing, Care of Older Adult, Care of Clients with Life Threatening Conditions, Acuity Ill/ Multi-Organ Progress High Acuity Emergency Situation, Acuity and Ill, Intensive Nursing Practicum, Nursing Research I, and Nursing Research II To Nursing Practice V.*

Table 27 Correlation of General Weighted Average of Medical Surgical Nursing I, Medical Surgical Nursing II, Nursing Leadership and Management, Disaster Nursing, Psychiatric Nursing, Care of Older Adult, Care of Clients with Life Threatening Conditions, Acuity Ill/ Multi-Organ Progress High Acuity Emergency Situation, Acuity and Ill, Intensive Nursing Practicum, Nursing Research I, and Nursing Research II to Nursing Practice V.

	Nursing Practice V	
	χ^2	
Medical Surgical Nursing I	10.99 ^{ns}	Medical Surgical Nursing I
Medical Surgical Nursing II	25.39 ^{ns}	Medical Surgical Nursing II
Nursing Leadership and Management	26.85 ^{ns}	Nursing Leadership and Management
Disaster Nursing	28.29*	Disaster Nursing
Psychiatric Nursing	37.33**	Psychiatric Nursing
Nursing research I	32.08 ^{ns}	Nursing research I
Nursing research II	11.25 ^{ns}	Nursing research II
Care of Older Adult	26.98*	Care of Older Adult
Care of Clients with Life threatening conditions, Acuity ill/ multi-organ progress High Acuity Emergency situation, Acuity and ill	30.96 ^{ns}	Care of Clients with Life threatening conditions, Acuity ill/ multi-organ progress High Acuity Emergency situation, Acuity and ill
Intensive Nursing Practicum	10.76 ^{ns}	Intensive Nursing Practicum

^{ns}- (Not significant)
 * (Significant)
 ** (Highly significant)

The table above shows the Correlation of General Weighted Average of Medical Surgical Nursing I, Medical Surgical Nursing II, Nursing Leadership and Management, Disaster Nursing, Psychiatric Nursing, Nursing research I, Nursing research II, Care of Older Adult, Care of Clients with Life threatening conditions, Acuity ill/ multi-organ progress High Acuity Emergency situation, Acuity and ill, and Intensive Nursing Practicum to Nursing Practice V, one of the components of Nursing Licensure Examination. It revealed that out of the nine subjects, only Disaster Nursing and Psychiatric Nursing gained a highly significant relationship with Nursing Practice V since the p-value of Nursing 421 is 0.029 and p value of Nursing 323 is 0.002 which is less than the level of significance 0.05. Therefore, the table above indicates that if Disaster Nursing and Psychiatric Nursing academic performance increases, the students board exam performance in NP V also increases. It is supported by the study of (Ong et.al., 2012 Presumptions of Nurses' Licensure Examination Performance of Graduates in Cebu Normal University, Philippines Ong, Palompon & Bañico Asian Journal of Health 140 consists of a strong predictive power of these variables. It is believed that students' learning in the classroom and clinical exposures during their four years in nursing predicted their performance in the licensure examination, plus the immediate influence of students' performance in the pre-board examination. These results can be attributed to the fact that nursing students have gained specialized competences over their four years of college. They have to have mastered all of these abilities in order to be recognized as holders of a Bachelor of Science in Nursing degree when they graduate.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

- *The following Conclusions were Made Considering the Findings:*
 - The results revealed that Intensive Nursing Practicum, Care of Older Adults, and Nursing Leadership and Management are the top three nursing professional subjects that has the highest mean of general weighted average. While Nursing Research I, Fundamentals of Nursing Practice and Medical Surgical Nursing I are the three nursing professional subjects that has lowest mean of general weighted average.
 - Out of five nursing practice test, Nursing Practice III has the lowest board exam rate of November 2022 NLE takers while Nursing Practice I have the highest board exam rate. Nursing Practice III can be considered as the hardest part of November 2022 NLE which covers the Medical Surgical Nursing, Psychiatric Nursing, Nursing research, Care of Clients with Life Threatening Conditions, Acutely Ill/Multi-Organ Problems, High Acuity and Emergency Situation, Acute and Ill, Nursing Leadership and Management, Care of Older Adult, Intensive Nursing Practicum, and Disaster Nursing.
 - The results revealed that Health Assessment has a significant relationship to Nursing Practice I, Disaster Nursing has significant relationship to Nursing Practice IV and V, and Care of Older Adult and Psychiatric Nursing has significant relationship to Nursing Practice V. The researchers concluded that as the respondents' academic performances in these subjects increases, their board exam performance also increases.

Tabale 28 Nursing Professional Subjects

Nursing Professional Subjects	NP1	NP2	NP3	NP4	NP5
1. Health Assessment					
2. Disaster Nursing					
3. Psychiatric Nursing					
4. Care of Older Adult					

Legend:

- Not significant
- Significant
- Highly Significant

RECOMMENDATIONS

- *The Researcher Offers the Following Implementation Suggestions Considering the Findings and Conclusions.*
 - In order to hasten the process of nursing students who are next in line to take the Nursing Licensure Examination (NLE) and for their future endeavor, clinical instructors should reinforce effective and creative teaching strategies or methods on subjects that have significant relationships to nursing test categories and to the subjects perceived as difficult by nursing graduates guided by the evaluation of the study for effective learning which will lead to improved board exam performance.

- The students should put in extra effort and work hard to get good results in professional subjects. They should also be encouraged to aim higher to earn a better board examination percentage because it affects the Nursing Licensure Examination.
- A parallel study can be conducted by future researchers to determine if there's still significant relationship of undergraduate professional subjects since Nursing Licensure Examination questions every year are unpredictable. It will serve as a basis for curriculum improvement. Moreover, when it comes to obtaining respondents, all of them should be PNLE passers.
- Future researchers can conduct a study that focuses on the factors affecting the board exam performance of nursing graduates. They can also conduct a study that

shows the relationship between the Related Learning Experience academic grades and the board exam performance of the nursing graduates to determine if there is an impact or bearing on the board exam performance.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Calma, R. R., & Maglaque, E. M. (2019). RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN IN-HOUSE REVIEW PERFORMANCE AND PERFORMANCE IN THE CPA LICENSURE EXAMINATIONS OF THE BSA GRADUATES FROM 2015 TO 2017.
- [2]. De Leon, J. M. (2016). Academic and licensure examination performances of BSN graduates: Bases for curriculum enhancement. <https://journalissues.org/ijepr/wpcontent/uploads/sites/7/2016/06/De-Leon.pdf>
- [3]. Journal, I. (n.d.). LEVEL OF ACCREDITATION AND BOARD PERFORMANCE OF THE COLLEGES OF NURSING IN THE NATIONAL CAPITAL REGION. www.academia.edu. Retrieved July 14, 2023, from https://www.academia.edu/36957330/LEVEL_OF_ACCREDITATION_AND_BOARD_PERFORMANCE_OF_THE_COLLEGES_OF_NURSING_IN_THE_NATIONAL_CAPITAL_REGION
- [4]. Lamasan, J. M. J., Lavadia, H. J. M., Limosnero, J. S., Magbitang, K. J. V., Mallari, M. J. B. S., Obado, A. C. C., Paguio, E. B., & Perez, J. G. (2018). CORRELATION OF ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE, NURSING LICENSURE EXAMINATION AND CORE COMPETENCY PERFORMANCE OF NURSING GRADUATES OF UPHSL 2013-2016. <https://www.herdin.ph/index.php?view=research&cid=68803>
- [5]. Lin, R. S. J., Fung, B. K. P., Hsiao, J.-K., & Lo, H.-F. (2016). Relationship between academic scores and performance on national qualified examination for registered professional nurses (NQEX-RPN). *Nurse Education Today*, 23(7), 492–497. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0260-6917\(03\)00073-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0260-6917(03)00073-x)
- [6]. Llego, J., Al- Saqrib, S., Gabriel, E., & Corpus, J. (2020). The Predictive Strength of Academic Performance in Passing the Philippine Nurse Licensure Examination [Review of The Predictive Strength of Academic Performance in Passing the Philippine Nurse Licensure Examination]. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, Volume 12(1). www.ijcc.net
- [7]. Ma Lorna A. Ignacio, Elizabeth V. Bantique, & Teresita S. Dela Pena. (2016). CORRELATES OF NURSE LICENSURE EXAMINATION (NLE): AN ANALYSIS OF BALIUAG UNIVERSITY BSN GRADUATES' PERFORMANCE. *Harvest*, 12(1), 1–1. <https://www.ejournals.ph/article.php?id=11596>
- [8]. Montegrigo, J., & Oducado, R. M. F. (2022). Scoping review of factors affecting Philippine nurse licensure examination outcomes. [Sigma.nursingrepository.org](http://sigma.nursingrepository.org). <https://hdl.handle.net/10755/22920>
- [9]. Neri, R. (2009). E-learning and General Weighted Average as Predictors for Nurses Licensure Examination. <https://journalissues.org/ijepr/wp-content/uploads/sites/7/2016/04/De-Leon-et-al.pdf>
- [10]. NLE RESULT: November 2022 nursing board exam list of passers. (n.d.). PRC Board News. <https://www.prcboardnews.com/2022/11/nle-result-november-2022-nursing-board-exam-list-of-passers.html>
- [11]. Nursing Board/Licensure Exam Answer Key: NP3 Nursing Board Exam November 2008 Answer Key “Nursing Care of Client with Physiological and Psychosocial Alteration.” (2010, June 27). Nursing Board/Licensure Exam Answer Key. https://nursingboardexamanswerkey.blogspot.com/2010/06/np3-nursing-board-exam-november-2008_27.html
- [12]. Oducado, R. M. F. O., Cendaña, D. P., & Delariarte, R. G. B. (2019). Institutional Competency Assessment and Other Factors Influencing the Nurse Licensure Examination. 8(12).
- [13]. Pacis, M., Fontanilla, D., Panopio, A., & Concepcion, L. (n.d.). Correlation analysis of selected academic parameters and the Nurse Licensure Examination performance of the National University-Manila BSN graduates. https://national-u.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/4.-JSTAR6_2-Panopio.pdf
- [14]. R&D Journal. (n.d.). [Journal.bicol-U.edu.ph](http://journal.bicol-u.edu.ph). https://journal.bicol-u.edu.ph/assets/journal_pdf/8%20Banua_113-118.pdf
- [15]. Soriano, G. P. (2016). Relationship between Academic Performance and the Nursing Licensure Examination of Graduates from a City-Subsidized University. 86, 56-62. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318493803_Relationship_between_Academic_Performance_and_the_Nursing_Licensure_Examination_of_Graduates_from_a_City-Subsidized_University